

Mediation of customer satisfaction: E-service quality, brand trust, and reuse intention

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explain the role of customer satisfaction in mediating e-service quality and brand trust on reuse intention in the Traveloka application. The theories used are the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory (EDT). This research is a type of quantitative research that is associative in nature. The population in this study are all Traveloka application users who have transacted at least three (3) times in one year. The sampling technique used purposive sampling with a total sample member of 205 respondents. Respondent data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires. The data analysis technique in this study used PLS-based SEM. The results showed that all variables had a positive and significant effect. Customer satisfaction acts as a partial mediation in mediating the effect of e-service quality and brand trust on reuse intention on the Traveloka application. The results of this study can provide an empirical contribution about the relationship between the variables of e-service quality, brand trust, customer satisfaction, and reuse intention for the development of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory (EDT). Traveloka management can implement a marketing strategy that emphasizes service quality and information accuracy to increase customer intention to reuse the Traveloka application.

Keywords: Reuse Intention; E-Service Quality; Brand Trust; Customer Satisfaction

1. Introduction

To create reuse intentions, companies that sell their products online certainly need to pay attention to the quality of digital services provided to customers. Hasman et al. (2019) state that e-service quality shows the company's ability to provide customer needs by utilizing the internet network. The quality of service on the internet network is an important factor in determining the success or failure of an e-commerce (Rohwiyati and Praptiestrini, 2019). Based on research from Sulistianingsih and Trishananto (2021), Pratiwi et al (2022), and Sembiring et al. (2023) state that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention. Different results were found by Waluya et al. (2019) and Ginting et al. (2022) which state that e-service quality has no significant effect on reuse intention.

Apart from e-service quality, a key factor in online buying and selling activities is trust (Masarianti and Darwini, 2019). Transactions in online shopping systems between sellers and buyers make trust an important role. According to Yolandari and Kusumadewi (2018), trust in brands is very important to maintain long-term online buying and selling relationships. Based on the results of research by Narahdita et al. (2020), Nelwan et al. (2021), and Febriani and Ardani (2021), show that trust has a significant positive effect on reuse intention. Different results were found in research by Masarianti and Darwini (2019) and Ikhsan and Lestari (2021), trust does not have a significant effect on reuse intention in the marketplace.

The results of previous studies find that there are gaps in research results regarding the effect of e-service quality and brand trust on reuse intention, therefore, to support the formation of reuse intention it is also important to pay attention

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to customer value and customer satisfaction. Based on the results of this study, to increase the intention to reuse it is important to create customer satisfaction (Rafiah, 2019). Satisfied customers will usually have a positive impression which will then trigger the intention to reuse. According to Lestari and Ellyawati (2019), and according to Ginting et al. (2022), state that customer satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of e-service quality on repurchase intention. These results indicate that in this study customer satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention. Research by Devi and Sulistyawati (2018), Sumara and Salim (2018), and Jayaputra and Kempa (2022), found that customer satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of trust on repurchase intention. These results indicate that in this study customer satisfaction is able to mediate the effect of brand trust on reuse intention.

Consumers will reuse and repurchase a product or service when the company is able to fulfill desires and is able to satisfy customers (Lestari and Hamid, 2020). This statement is in accordance with previous research, namely according to Hasman et al. (2019), Rohwiyati and Praptiestrini (2019), and Rahayu and Saodin (2021), customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention or in this study is the intention to reuse. Different results were found in the research of Ongkowijoyo (2022), and Yusuf (2022) which stated that customer satisfaction does not have a significant effect on customer intention to repurchase, which in this study is reuse intention.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Hasman et al. (2019) state that e-service quality shows the company's ability to provide customer needs by utilizing the internet network. The quality of service on the internet network is an important factor in determining the success or failure of an e-commerce (Rohwiyati and Praptiestrini, 2019). Based on research from Sulistianingsih and Trishananto (2021), Pratiwi et al. (2022), and Sembiring et al. (2023) state that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention. These results indicate that the better the quality of the e-service provided, the more customers' intention to reuse a product or service increases. Different results were found by Waluya et al. (2019) and Ginting et al. (2022) which state that e-service quality has no significant effect on reuse intention.

2.1. H1: E-service quality has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention.

The key factor in online buying and selling activities is trust (Masarianti and Darwini, 2019). According to Yolandari and Kusumadewi (2018), trust in brands is very important to maintain long-term online buying and selling relationships. Based on the results of research by Narahdita et al. (2020), Nelwan et al. (2021), Febriani and Ardani (2021), Prayudi et al. (2022), and Lufiati and Suparna (2023), show that trust has a significant positive effect on reuse intention. These results identify that the higher the customer's trust in a brand, the higher the intention to reuse a product or service. Different results were found in research by Masarianti and Darwini (2019) and Ikhsan and Lestari (2021), trust does not have a significant effect on reuse intention in the marketplace. Based on the results of empirical studies, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

2.2. H2: Brand trust has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention.

Reuse intention occurs after getting what is expected more than expectations (Prakosa and Wintaka, 2020). According to Zhang and Kim (2021), reuse intention arises when the performance of the product/service is in accordance with the expected benefits so that this determines consumer satisfaction and generates reuse intention. Consumers will reuse and repurchase a product or service when the company is able to fulfill desires and is able to satisfy customers (Lestari and Hamid, 2020). Based on Hasman et al. (2019), Rohwiyati and Praptiestrini (2019), Rahayu and Saodin (2021), Natalia and Suparna (2023), and Dwijayanti et al. (2023), customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intentions or reuse intentions. This identifies that the higher the customer satisfaction, the higher the customer's intention to reuse a product or service. Different results were found in the research of Ongkowijoyo (2022), and Yusuf (2022) which stated that customer satisfaction does not have a significant effect on consumer intention to repurchase, which in this study is the intention to reuse.

2.3. H3: Customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention.

Good service quality will create customer satisfaction (Lestari and Ellyawati, 2019). Research by Hasman et al. (2019) states that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. The same results were obtained from the research of Rohwiyati and Praptiestrini (2019), Rahayu and Saodin (2021), and Morsi (2023), that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. These results identify that the better the quality of e-service provided, the higher customer satisfaction. Different results were found in the research of Ciputra and Prasetya (2020), namely e-service quality has no significant effect on customer satisfaction.

2.4. H4: E-service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction.

According to Yolandari and Kusumadewi (2018) trust is very important for long-term online business relationships. Building trust has an impact on customer satisfaction (Yolandari and Kusumadewi, 2018). This theory is supported by the results of research from Diputra and Yasa (2021), Hamzah (2021), and Rahmawati (2021), namely brand trust has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction. This identifies that the higher the customer's trust in the brand, the higher the customer satisfaction. Different results were found in the research of Kartika and Soenarmi (2019), namely trust has a positive but insignificant effect on customer satisfaction. Based on the results of empirical studies, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

2.5. H5: Brand trust has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction

Zeithaml et al. (2018) state that customer satisfaction or customer satisfaction is a reaction to the satisfaction of customer desires for a product or service that satisfies according to the customer's own expectations. According to Zhang and Kim (2021), reuse intention arises when the performance of the product/service is in accordance with the expected benefits so that this determines consumer satisfaction and gives rise to reuse intention. This theory is in line with the results of research by Lestari and Ellyawati (2019), Anggraini et al. (2020), Jasin and Firmansyah (2022), Dayani et al. (2022) and Ginting et al. (2022), state that customer satisfaction can mediate the effect of e-service quality on repurchase intention. These results indicate that the effect of e-service quality is stronger on reuse intention with the mediation of customer satisfaction. Based on the results of empirical studies, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

2.6. H6: Customer satisfaction is able to positively and significantly mediate the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention.

According to Lestari and Hamid (2020), consumers will reuse and repurchase a product or service when the company is able to fulfill desires and be able to satisfy customers. Research by Devi and Sulistyawati (2018), Sumara and Salim (2018), and Jayaputra and Kempa (2022), found that customer satisfaction can mediate the effect of trust on repurchase intention. These results indicate that the effect of brand trust is stronger on reuse intention with mediation from customer satisfaction.

H7: Customer satisfaction can positively and significantly mediate the effect of brand trust on reuse intention.

3. Methods

The subjects of this research are Traveloka customers who have made transactions on the Traveloka application at least 3 times within 1 year with a minimum age of 18 years and reside in Denpasar. The research objects studied include the quality of electronic services provided by Traveloka to customers, customer trust in Traveloka, customer satisfaction, and customer reuse intentions in the Traveloka application. The population in this study are all Traveloka customers in Denpasar who have shopped at Traveloka e-commerce at least 3 times within one year, which is infinite. According to Hair et al. (2017: 176), if the population is unknown, you can calculate the sample size by (5-10) times the number of variable measurement indicators. The variable measurement indicators used in this study totaled 31 so that the sample size was in the range of 155 to a maximum of 310 respondents. This study used the maximum sample, namely 310 respondents to avoid a sample shortage when there were questionnaire answers that did not meet the research criteria. The sampling method used in this research is nonprobability sampling. The nonprobability sampling technique chosen is purposive sampling, which is a sampling technique with certain considerations (Sugiyono, 2021: 144). The sample criteria in this study are as follows:

- At least 18 years old
- The last education is high school / equivalent
- Reside in Denpasar
- Have transacted in the Traveloka application at least 3 times within 1 year

Data analysis was carried out using the Partial Least Square (PLS) method using SmartPLS software version 3. PLS is one of the methods of solving Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) which in this case is more compared to other SEM techniques.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Evaluation of the structural model or inner model

Inner model analysis is a structural model that ensures that the structural model is strong and accurate. The following Figure 1 is a path diagram of the structural model (inner model).

Figure 1 Structural Model

4.2. R-square

The calculation of the R-Square (R²) value aims to see how much the correlation value of the endogenous variables resulting from the PLS estimation of each path (Hair et al., 2017: 213). The R-square (R²) value ranges from 0 to 1, assuming the higher the R-square value, the better the research structural model. The results of the R-square value can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1 R-Square

Variable	R Square
Customer satisfaction	0.560
Reuse intention	0.709

Primary Data, 2024

Based on Table 1, the R-square value of the customer satisfaction variable is 0.560. This means that 56 percent of the variability of the customer satisfaction construct can be explained by the e-service quality and brand trust variables, while the remaining 44 percent of the customer satisfaction variable is explained by other variables outside the model. Likewise, the reuse intention variable has an R-square value of 0.709. This means that 70.9 percent of the variability of the reuse intention construct can be explained by the e-service quality, brand trust, and customer satisfaction variables, while the remaining 29.1 percent of the reuse intention variable is explained by other variables outside the model.

4.3. Q-Square predictive relevance

Inner model testing is done by looking at the Structural Model Evaluation value through Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²). Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) is a measure of how well the observations made give results to the research model. The Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) value ranges from 0 (zero) to 1 (one). The closer to 0 the Q-Square Predictive Relevance (Q²) value is, it indicates that the research model is getting worse, on the other hand, the further away from 0 (zero) and the closer to the value of 1 (one), this means that the research model is getting better. The model of the effect of e-service quality, brand trust, and customer satisfaction on reuse intention provides an R-square value as listed in Table 1.

$$\begin{aligned} Q^2 &= 1 - (1 - R^2_1)(1 - R^2_2) \\ &= 1 - (0.440)(0.291) \\ &= 1 - 0.128 = 0.872 \end{aligned}$$

The result of the Q² calculation is 0.872, meaning that 87.2 percent of the reuse intention variable in the Traveloka application has a relevant predictive value of 87.2 percent because it can explain the information in this study and is classified as very strong.

4.4. Goodness of Fit (GoF)

This GoF value is obtained from the square root of the product of the average variance extracted (AVE) value and the average R-square (R²) value. The GoF criteria are in the value range 0 (zero) - 1 (one) with the interpretation of the value, namely 0.1 (small GoF), 0.25 (moderate GoF), and 0.36 (large GoF). The following is the calculation of Goodness of Fit in testing the structural model.

$$\begin{aligned} GoF &= \sqrt{\overline{AVE} \times \overline{R^2}} \\ \overline{AVE} &= \text{average AVE} = 0,845 \\ \overline{R^2} &= \text{average } R^2 = 0,635 \\ GoF &= \sqrt{\overline{AVE} \times \overline{R^2}} \\ GoF &= \sqrt{0,845 \times 0,635} \\ GoF &= 0,732 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the results of these calculations, the GoF value is 0.732, which means that the research model already has a large GoF value. This value affects the goodness of the structural model in this study. The overall test of the structural model (inner model) obtained good results, so that this structural model was declared good and was able to provide predictive power for the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables in this study.

4.5. Hypothesis Testing

Based on the results of the PLS analysis, it shows the direction and influence of each independent variable on the dependent variable. These results can be described as follows:

Table 2 Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Original Sampel (O)	p values	Result
E-service quality -> Reuse intention	0.183	0.002	Accepted
Brand trust -> Reuse intention	0.307	0.000	Accepted
Customer satisfaction -> Reuse intention	0.457	0.000	Accepted
E-service quality -> Customer satisfaction	0.495	0.000	Accepted
Brand trust -> Customer satisfaction	0.326	0.000	Accepted
E-service quality -> Customer satisfaction -> Reuse intention	0.226	0.000	Accepted
Brand trust -> Customer satisfaction -> Reuse intention	0.149	0.000	Accepted

Primary Data, 2024

4.6. E-service quality on reuse intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention produce an original sample value of 0.183, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that e-service quality on reuse intention has a positive effect. The pvalues value of $0.002 < 0.05$ indicates that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention or H1 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the e-service quality variable, the value of the reuse intention variable will also increase significantly.

4.7. Brand trust on reuse intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of brand trust on reuse intention produce an original sample value of 0.307, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that brand trust on reuse intention has a positive effect. The pvalues value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that brand trust has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention or H2 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the brand trust variable, the value of the reuse intention variable will also increase significantly.

4.8. Customer satisfaction on reuse intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of customer satisfaction on reuse intention produce an original sample value of 0.457, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that customer satisfaction on reuse intention has a positive effect. The pvalues value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention or H3 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the customer satisfaction variable, the value of the reuse intention variable will also increase significantly.

4.9. E-service quality on customer satisfaction

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of e-service quality on customer satisfaction produce an original sample value of 0.495, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that e-service quality on customer satisfaction has a positive effect. The pvalues value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction or H5 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the e-service quality variable, the value of the customer satisfaction variable will also increase significantly.

4.10. Brand trust on customer satisfaction

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of brand trust on customer satisfaction produce an original sample value of 0.326, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that brand trust on customer satisfaction has a positive effect. The pvalues value of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicates that brand trust has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction or H5 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the brand trust variable, the value of the customer satisfaction variable will also increase significantly.

4.11. Customer satisfaction mediate E-service quality on reuse intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention through customer satisfaction as mediation produce an original sample value of 0.226, which shows a positive number, so it can be explained that e-service quality on reuse intention through customer satisfaction as mediation has a positive effect.

The p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$ indicate that e-service quality has a positive and significant effect on reuse intention through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable or H6 is accepted. This result also means that the higher the value of the e-service quality variable, the value of the reuse intention variable through customer satisfaction will also increase significantly.

4.12. Customer satisfaction mediate brand trust on reuse intention

Based on Table 2, it can be seen that the results of the effect of brand trust on reuse intention through customer satisfaction as mediation produce an original sample value of 0.149, which shows a positive number, so that it can be explained that brand trust on reuse intention through customer satisfaction is significant.

4.13. Testing the Role of Mediating

The role of mediating shows the relationship between independent and dependent variables through connecting or mediating variables. The effect of variables on dependent variables does not occur directly but through a transformation process represented by the mediating variable. Calculating VAF with the formula is as follows:

$$\text{VAF} = (\text{indirect effect}) / (\text{direct effect} + \text{indirect effect})$$

If the VAF value is above 80 percent, it shows the role of M as a full mediator (full mediation). M is categorized as a partial mediator if the VAF value ranges from 20 percent to 80 percent, but if the VAF value is less than 20 percent, it means that there is almost no mediation effect.

The role of customer satisfaction in mediating the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention is as follows:

$$\text{VAF} = (\text{Indirect effect}) / (\text{Direct effect} + \text{Indirect effect})$$

$$= 0.226 / (0.183 + 0.226)$$

$$= 0.552 (55.2\%)$$

Based on the VAF test, the calculated value of 55.2 percent, which is between 20 percent and 80 percent, can be categorized as a partial mediation. Based on these results, customer satisfaction partially mediates the effect of e-service quality on reuse intention, which means that e-service quality can effect reuse intention with or without going through customer satisfaction.

The role of customer satisfaction in mediating the effect of brand trust on reuse intention is as follows:

$$\text{VAF} = (\text{Indirect effect}) / (\text{Direct effect} + \text{Indirect effect})$$

$$= 0.149 / (0.307 + 0.149)$$

$$= 0.326 (32.6\%)$$

Based on the VAF test, the calculated value of 32.6 percent, which is between 20 percent and 80 percent, can be categorized as a partial mediation. Based on these results, customer satisfaction partially mediates the effect of brand trust on reuse intention, which means that brand trust can effect reuse intention with or without going through customer satisfaction.

5. Conclusion

E-service quality and brand trust can affect customer satisfaction and can affect reuse intention. The results of the mediation test in this study also obtained empirical evidence stating that customer satisfaction can mediate the influence of e-service quality and brand trust on reuse intention. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) formed by the perception of benefits and perception of ease is related to Expectancy Disconfirmation Theory (EDT) regarding a person's satisfaction and dissatisfaction will form an intention. Intention then affects how a person behaves. With this theory as the basis for the current study, it can analyze the influence of intention on the behavior of decisions to reuse an application.

5.1. Managerial Implication

This research is expected to be a consideration and input for e-commerce parties, especially Traveloka in improving customer satisfaction and reuse intention on the application. A deep understanding of how e-service quality and brand trust affect reuse intention through customer satisfaction can help management optimize marketing, operational, and risk management strategies. Management can conduct consistent marketing campaigns on social media by highlighting positive testimonials from satisfied tourists. Management must focus on aspects such as service quality, product reliability, effectiveness of application use, security, and building customer trust so that it can help build customer satisfaction.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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